

ExAMPLER Community Report

Exascale Agent-Based Modelling for Policy Evaluation in Real-Time

Alison Heppenstall, Gary Polhill, Michael Batty, Matt Hare, Ricardo Colasanti, Doug Salt and Richard Milton

Summary

Pandemic, war, cost of living crisis, climate emergency, increased pressures on key services, improving public health. These are just a few of the societal issues that have arisen in the past few years. Governments, national agencies etc do not currently have the tools to formulate evidence-driven policy on the fly (as shown by the UK response to Covid). This is despite there being an abundance in data, theory, methodological innovations and advances in computational processing power to facilitate large complex models being run at scale in real time. If all these essential materials are in place, what other barriers need to be overcome within computational social science to translate robust small scale ‘desktop’ models onto large scale computing for real-time rapid response modelling?

The ExAMPLER (Exascale agent-based modelling for policy evaluation in real-time) project was an 18 month project (funded by UKRI) that has worked within the agent-based social simulation (ABSS) community to:

- i) identify community visions of the opportunities and barriers (in the form of potential new modelling capabilities, novel use cases, capacity requirements and potential threats) associated with implementing exascale ABSS (Hare et al., 2024); and
- ii) draft a roadmap (Milton et al., 2025), based on these visions, that further examines the (a) barriers, opportunities and (b) steps that need to be realised for the ABSS community to reap the benefits of exascale computing.

A note on nomenclature: Computational social science is the name given to the community with which we have engaged. Even though in this document we refer to this community as doing Agent-Based Social Simulation (ABSS), it should be noted that this includes researchers who use develop and apply agent-based models for understanding and simulating social systems as well as proponents of other computational approaches (microsimulation, Individual-Based Modelling, etc).

Urban
Big
Data
Centre

The James
Hutton
Institute

CASA

Background

Understanding the dynamics of urban environments requires careful consideration of *who* the people are, *where* they are going, *what* they are doing, and *why* they are doing it. These questions are of central importance to urban planners, as insights into the dynamics of cities enable the design and testing of targeted interventions. Such interventions may include the implementation of new transport infrastructures, decarbonisation initiatives, or policies like dynamic car park pricing. However, identifying who is affected by these changes—particularly those who may be negatively impacted—requires more than aggregate statistics. Accurately piecing together the who, what, where, and why of urban activity is a complex challenge that demands novel data sources, fine-grained behavioural insight, and an emphasis on individual-level analysis.

One stream of thought within the wider academic discipline of urban analytics highlights the role of the individual in shaping the processes and drivers that shape cities. This type of thought firmly puts individuals at the centre of any model and requires a method that allows the creation of heterogeneous individuals and behaviours. A method that has gained a great deal of popularity in the last 20 years is agent-based social simulation (ABSS). ABSS allows such heterogeneous individuals to be created and situated in realistic environments (Figure 1). New ideas, interactions, exchanges of information emerge from non-linear interactions.

Figure 1. Diagrammatic representation of (a) individual agent; (b) agents interacting within an environment; (c) representation of urban environment. (Images taken from The Sims)

This move towards bottom-up modelling marks a change from viewing cities with a ‘top down’ lens. Embedded with this change in thinking are the concepts of complexity (a system in which many interconnected parts interact in non-linear and often unpredictable ways), systems thinking (an approach to understanding problems by viewing them as part of an overall system, recognising interdependencies and feedback loops), tipping points (critical thresholds where a small change can lead to a significant and often irreversible shift in the system's behaviour) and cascading consequences (a chain of events triggered by an initial change that causes a series of further impacts throughout a system). This change in how we conceptualise cities aligns with the movement towards digital twins (DTs). In their most simplistic form, DTs seek to represent systems or processes in digital form. They have been used extensively within engineering and medical sciences, but increased attention has been placed upon digital twins of cities or urban areas. If we can successfully recreate the processes and drivers within our cities, decision and policy makers have a tool at their disposal for planning around unexpected events or exploring cascading consequences of new policies. However, producing a robust and representative urban digital twin presents many issues which will not be discussed here. Of relevance are the requirements of great amounts of granular data, computational power and storage.

Computational social science is advancing at a rapid pace with developments in theory, new fine resolution data sets and modelling frameworks for testing and simulating different phenomena. However, as evidenced from the ExAMPLER SLR, only 5% of models were run on HPCs (Polhill et al. in prep.); though in fact the real result is that the computing environment is typically not reported – this being the case in 87% of papers reviewed. The 5% figure assumes that if not reported, personal computing devices were used. There are a few papers not picked up in the SLR using FLAME GPU (Richmond et al. 2021), and Axtell et al.’s (2016) work using GPUs natively, but GPU programming for ABMs is virtually zero as a fraction of the community, and we could find no examples of exascale ABM. Bridging the gap between small scale (representations of streets and villages) models run on desktops to large scale (cities) models at exascale would have a transformative impact on computational social science. Urban digital twins could be run at scale and in real-time allowing rapid responses to pressing questions.

Exascale computing resources are beginning to come online, the first Exascale computer “Frontier” is installed and working at Oak Ridge National Laboratories (US), with several others near to completion. Whilst the planned UK exascale computing was briefly put on hold by the new Labour government, the project to build the UK’s first exascale computer is now under way. Preparing the UK community to exploit this resource for scientific research is thus a high priority.

Engagement activities – visions workshops

Over the course of ExAMPLER, we held two visions workshops and two roadmap workshops (Table 1) that were focused on engaging the computational social simulation community working on ABSS.

Table 1. Overview of ExAMPLER’s Visions and Roadmap Workshops

Workshop	Location & Date	Key questions	Participants
Visions workshop 1	Social Simulation Conference, University of Glasgow, 4 th September 2023	How could exascale computing transform the way in which ABSS is used? What potential capabilities and use cases can it provide researchers? What capacities are required to achieve exascale ABSS? What are the threats to achieving this and the possible threats created by its achievement?	27 self-selecting international conference participants from the academic ABSS community representing 10 different countries
Visions workshop 2	UCL, 8-9 th November 2023	As above.	14 invited participants from academia and industry (UK-centred)
Roadmap workshop 1	University of Glasgow, 29 – 30 th April 2024	Given the visions, what needs to be done, technically, to achieve exascale Agent-Based Social Simulation, e.g. through making the most of accelerator capabilities (parallelisation)?	12 invited participants from academia and industry (UK-centred)
Roadmap workshop 2	Social Simulation Conference, Cracow University of Economics, 16 th September 2024	As above.	14 self-selected international conference participants from the academic ABSS community

In addition to these planned events, ExAMPLER also engaged with the community in a number of other extra events. These are listed in Appendix 1.

Potential exascale ABSS use cases and threats

The following potential uses cases were extracted from the visions workshops and are summarised below. More information on the results of the visions workshops are available in Hare et al. (2024) and in a journal article currently being co-authored with the participants of the visions workshops (Hare et al. in prep).

1. **Scaling-up and the development of very fine-detailed, very large scale ABSS:** the speed and computational power of exascale computing would provide ABSS model developers greater capabilities for simulating individual human activities and social interactions across very large geographical spaces and social networks.
2. **Individual-based social science as an emerging field:** with increased capability to develop very large scale ABSS and to explore such models (i.e. improved validation, uncertainty quantification, running models in real time), there might be no reason for ABSS not to develop as a social science in its own right.
3. **Better modelling of social behaviour by identifying the best formalisation for social science theories:** With the ability to run multiple model parameterisations, there is the opportunity to explore different options for formalising social theories and to test their efficacy, *in silico* This would lead to better modelling of social behaviour as well as better social science.
4. **Real-time decision-making support:** The original vision of the ExAMPLER project was that access to an exascale computer would mean insights from simulations would take fractions of a second to gain, which would mean that ABSS could be embedded in real-time as part of creative policy and decision-making discussions on how to handle a developing crisis (e.g. COVID).
5. **Meta-modelling and general simulation emulators:** The ability to perform larger numbers of runs allows the possibility of generating data from simulations that can be used to train high-quality metamodels and emulators.
6. **Real-time visualisation and debugging tools:** Faster and multiple runs will help fix bugs within software. New tools developed for this work can also be rolled out for real-time visualisation

Threats to these use cases:

1. **Increased energy consumption and cost:** The power required to get Frontier to exascale is 21 MW! It would use in an hour what two households would get through in a year for heating, lighting and cooking. (DEZNO, 2024)
2. **Overly complex models and insufficient data:** There is a danger that exascale computing could also mean (unnecessarily) bigger, upscaled, models just 'because we can', despite the difficulties that would be had in terms of getting hold of the high quality data that such models might require.
3. **Inefficient use of exascale resources:** Can the computational social science community take full advantage of exascale resources, is parallelism possible?

4. **Loss of research community control over agent-based modelling:** If emulators are fully developed, does this may mean that industry and/or policy users of ABSS do not consult researchers anymore. This could lead to non-experts drawing overgeneralized or incorrect conclusions.
5. **A lack of Research Software Engineers:** A lot of RSEs will be needed to support members of the ABSS community to get their models running on exascale computing resources. There might be insufficient resources available to properly fund the required numbers of RSEs to provide such support.
6. **Over-specialisation:** Another potential loss of control for the community relates to reliance on highly-specialised technical skills to get the models running on exascale frameworks. There is a fear that the technical component of the task of building exascale ABSS will begin to dominate the social science component.
7. **Over-zealous gatekeeping:** A further threat potentially comes from regulations and norms - determining exascale computer access (i.e. resource 'gatekeeping') - creating barriers that obstruct members of the ABSS community (from both the global north and south) from accessing exascale computing resources.
8. **Over-reliance on AI for development and interpretation:** Larger models and larger volumes of runs will result in vast quantities of complex outputs to analyse. This is a gap that developments within AI and machine learning could fill. However, there is also the real possibility that individuals could use Large Language Models e.g. Chat-GPT to assemble overly complicated models, and then analyse their outputs using AI. This would greatly impact on transferability and transparency of models, thereby reducing confidence in the outputs of such models.

Towards a Roadmap – Challenges of embedding exascale computing in ABSS

Figure 2 summarises a number of the challenges that the computational social simulation (ABSS) community needs to overcome to embed exascale in our activities. These challenges emerged as one of the outputs of the roadmap workshops (see Table 1) and are further explained below. Additional challenges are outlined in the accompanying Roadmap.

1. **Access GPU:** specific skills that are not part of any computational social science curriculum are required to access GPUs e.g. port Netlogo to GPUs; FlameGPU
2. **Non-standard equipment:** this is typically difficult to order through Universities and needs to be streamlined.
3. **HPC requests:** As a computational social scientist, making a successful request requires information on forms that we cannot give. For example, due to the nature of agent-based models (interactions, non-linear interactions), it is virtually impossible to input how much memory is required in advance.
4. **Justify investment:** Partly related to point 2, the computational social science community have to provide a more robust justification of requiring access to these resources than our colleagues in the 'harder' sciences.

5. **Reusable software:** Patterns, specifications and standards that can be reimplemented by anyone on their preferred platform. Standard driven software stacks.
6. **Overcome imposter syndrome and discrimination (Equality, Diversity, Inclusivity):** Several of the ExAMPLER team sit on various research panels and have noted that applications often only pay lip-service to this area. EDI is possibly one of the most important pillars of any research community and should be taken seriously e.g. when considering equitable access to exascale computing resources.

Figure 2. Summary of the main challenges facing the computational social simulation community.

An additional point that was raised both in the workshops and through work undertaken for the systematic literature review was **confusion over what can be labelled an agent-based model**. Without more terminological clarity in this area, the risk remains that ABSS will be improperly considered as an ill-defined activity not worthy of access to exascale resources (Polhill et al. in press).

Expected benefits

The goal of computational social simulation is to recreate key processes and drivers within the real system. This can range from understanding voter preference, consumer behaviour and preferences, individual movement around cities and of course, the creation of urban digital twins (Figure 3).

Figure 3. (a) the ‘real’ city; (b) NetLogo Schelling model representation; and (c) ChatGPT depiction of an urban digital twin. (Acknowledgement: Richard Milton)

By supporting the computing social science (ABSS) community in its move to exascale computation, there are a number of benefits that can be realised (see Hare et al. (2024) and the RoadMap (Milton et al. (2025) for further details):

For policy-makers

- Evidenced-based decision making using exascale computation that allows real-time, robust modelling of interventions.

For the public

- Trust in models from the computational social science community
- Greater transparency in models, therefore input and engagement (citizen science)

For researchers

- Scaling up of models
- Greater robustness in model validation and uncertainty quantification
- Integration of AI approaches (and ‘big data’ sources)
- Development of community-wide standards
- Development and testing of improved social theories
- Development of a new field: Individual-Based Social Science

For the exascale community

- Greater inclusivity in terms of supporting the provision of wider access to exascale resources
 - for more disciplines
 - for researchers from the global south as well as the global north

References not in outputs list (Appendix 1)

Axtell R. L. (2016) 120 million agents self-organize into 6 million firms: a model of the U.S. private sector. In Thanagarajah, J., Tuyls, K., Jonker, C., Marsella, S. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Autonomous Agents and Multiagent Systems (AAMAS 2016), May 9-13, 2016, Singapore*. <https://www.ifaamas.org/Proceedings/aamas2016/pdfs/p806.pdf>

DEZNO (2024) *Subnational electricity and gas consumption summary report 2024*. <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/subnational-electricity-and-gas-consumption-summary-report-2024/subnational-electricity-and-gas-consumption-summary-report-2024--2>

Richmond, P., Chisholm, R., Heywood, P., Leach, M., Kabiri Chimeh, M. (2021) FLAME GPU. *Zenodo*, doi: [10.5281/ZENODO.5428984](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5428984).

Appendix 1: Engagement activities

Additional workshops

- Nick Roxburgh, Gary Polhill, Alison Heppenstall, Mike Batty, Matt Hare, Doug Salt, Ric Colasanti and Richard Milton, A roadmap to Exascale computing in coupled socio-environmental modelling of complex systems. Workshop at Environmental Modelling and Software Society's Biennial Congress. Michigan State University, US, 23 – 27 June 2024

Conference presentations

- [Poster on ExAMPLER](#) at SSC 2023, September 2023
- [Presenting ExAMPLER at an invited talk](#) to the [First NHR Conference in Berlin](#), September 2023
- [Presentation on ExAMPLER](#) at the [SPF ExCALIBUR Programme-wide workshop in Bristol](#), October 2023
- Presentation: Alison Heppenstall, Gary Polhill, Mike Batty, Matt hare, Doug Salt, Richard Milton and Ricardo Colasanti “Exascale agent-based modelling for policy evaluation in real-time (ExAMPLER)”. GIScience. Leeds (UK), September 2023
- Presentation at the [ExCALIBUR project overview and update session](#) at the [Computing Insight UK conference in Manchester](#), December 2023
- Poster presentation: Matt Hare, Doug Salt, Ricardo Colasanti, Richard Milton, Michael Batty, Alison Heppenstall, Gary Polhill. “Taking Agent-Based Social Simulation to the Next Level Using Exascale Computing: Potential Use-Cases, Capacity Requirements and Threats” at the 23rd International Conference on Autonomous Agents and Multiagent Systems. AAMAS '24.
- Presentation: Alison Heppenstall, Gary Polhill, Mike Batty, Matt hare, Doug Salt, Richard Milton and Ricardo Colasanti “[Exascale agent-based modelling for policy evaluation in real-time \(ExAMPLER\)](#)”. Association of American Geographers Annual Conference. Hawai'i (US) April 2024
- Presentation: Matt Hare, Doug Salt, Ricardo Colasanti, Richard Milton, Michael Batty, Alison Heppenstall, Gary Polhill. “Revealing visions of the future of exascale Agent-Based Social Simulation (ABSS) using participatory systems modelling”. 19th Social Simulation Conference 2024, Cracow University of Economics, Poland. September 2024.

Invited events

- Alison Heppenstall and Gary Polhill. [Challenges and opportunities of using ABMs for simulating social systems](#). Exposome.NL Conference in Utrecht, November 2023, Netherlands. **Keynote talk.**
- Alison Heppenstall, Gary Polhill, Mike Batty, Matt hare, Doug Salt, Richard Milton and Ricardo Colasanti, Using HPC to model policy scenarios with agent-based models. Durham HPC Days. June 2024. Durham (UK)

- Gary Polhill, Alison Heppenstall, Mike Batty, Matt Hare, Doug Salt, Ric Colasanti and Richard Milton, Exascale computing and agent-based social simulation (ABSS). Computing Insight UK Conference, Manchester, UK. Dec 2023.
- Matt Hare, Gary Polhill, Alison Heppenstall, Mike Batty, Matt Hare, Doug Salt, Ric Colasanti and Richard Milton, ExAMPLER: taking agent-based social simulation to the next level with Exascale computing. SPF ExCALIBUR Programme-wide workshop, Bristol, UK. October 2023.

Training

- Agent-based modelling in the interface between economics and behavioral psychology. NTNU, Trondheim. 7-11/10/24.
- High Performance Computing for Agent-Based modelling. EASSS, University College Dublin, Ireland. 30/08/24.
- HPC for agent-based modellers. Two-day training course at The Hutton Institute (29/02/24 – 01/03/24)

Outputs (publications and conference proceedings)

- Gary Polhill, Alison Heppenstall, Michael Batty, Doug Salt, Ricardo Colasanti, Richard Milton and Matt Hare (2023) Exascale computing and ‘next generation’ agent-based modelling. Review of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation.
- Alison Heppenstall et al. “Exascale Agent-Based Modelling for Policy Evaluation in Real-Time (ExAMPLER)”. In: 12th International Conference on Geographic Information Science (GIScience 2023). Ed. by Roger Beecham et al. Vol. 277. Leibniz International Proceedings in Informatics (LIPIcs). Dagstuhl, Germany: Schloss Dagstuhl – Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik, 2023, 38:1–38:5. doi: [10.4230/LIPIcs.GIScience.2023.38](https://doi.org/10.4230/LIPIcs.GIScience.2023.38).
- Matt Hare et al. “Taking Agent-Based Social Simulation to the Next Level Using Exascale Computing: Potential Use-Cases, Capacity Requirements and Threats”. In: Proceedings of the 23rd International Conference on Autonomous Agents and Multiagent Systems. AAMAS ’24. Auckland, New Zealand: International Foundation for Autonomous Agents and Multiagent Systems, 2024, pp. 2300–2302.
- Milton, R. (2025). ExAMPLER Exascale ABMSS Roadmap (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15112700>
- G. Polhill, A. Heppenstall, M. Batty, M. Hare, R. Colasanti, D. Salt, R. Milton, S. Wise, K. Narasimhan, and Y. Gamalaldin. A proposed nomenclature for models of complex systems. In H. Verhagen, E. Chappin, and G. Scholz, editors, Advances in Social Simulation: Proceedings of the 20th Social Simulation Conference, Delft, The Netherlands, 25-29 August 2025, in press

Outputs in preparation

- Gary Polhill et al. “Where is the computation in the computational social sciences!? Exploring the potential demand for high-performance computing in our community through a systematic literature review.” To be submitted to the Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation.
- Matt Hare et al. “What could exascale computing ever do for us? Community visions of the future of exascale agent-based social simulation.” To be submitted to Journal of Simulation

Funding applications

- Netlogo Exascale meeting. ECP/USA ExCALIBUR collaboration programme. Alison Heppenstall and Gary Polhill. £2766.10. **Funded.**
- Accessible GPU-Accelerated Synthetic Population Generation (Pop GPU) - Resubmission. Safe by EPCC. £332601. PI: Alison Heppenstall and Gary Polhill. Submitted Sept 2024. Rejected.
- Accessible GPU-Accelerated Synthetic Population Generation (Pop GPU). Safe by EPCC. PI: Alison Heppenstall and Gary Polhill. £240K. Submitted Feb 2024. Rejected.
- APP35952 Make ARCHER2 NetLogo Ready (MANR) SDR UK Data Services. PI: Gary Polhill. Submitted March 2024. Rejected.
- APP83260: RADIANCE: Rapid Agent-based Decision Intelligence for Adaptive emergeNt Scenario Evaluation. PI: Gary Polhill. Submitted 28 November 2025. Rejected.
- APP46895: UKRI Living Benchmarks: skills to maximise the value of Digital Research Infrastructure investments. PI: Garth Wells. **Funded.**
- APP80987: Insights from Agent-Based Simulation at Scale. PI: Gary Polhill. Submitted March 2025. Rejected.

Photo credit: Richard Milton

Suggested Citation

Heppenstall, A., Polhill, G., Batty, M., Hare, M., Colasanti, R., Salt, D. and Milton, R. (2026) ExAMPLER Community Report. *Zenodo*

Contacts

Alison Heppenstall alison.heppenstall@glasgow.ac.uk

Gary Polhill gary.polhill@hutton.ac.uk

Matt Hare matt.hare@hutton.ac.uk

Mike Batty m.batty@ucl.ac.uk

This research is funded by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council, Grant Number EP/Y008839/1, with support from the Scottish Government Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division (project reference JHI-C5-1).

The views expressed are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the Scottish Government or the EPSRC.